

Enhancing Sustainability for Component Based software development through effective Component Retrieval and Reuse.

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Abstract

Software industry is growing like a global market and people across the globe asking for rapid development of software in very less time and budget. Component-Based Software Development (CBSD) approach has emerged as the answer for above challenges faced by software developer community. It concentrates on reusing and adapting existing software components instead of developing everything from scratch. The architectural design of the component-based software (CBS) plays a determining role in which components are merged to form a software application. Once the architectural design is established then the development team verifies the requirements to establish what subsets of the requirements are directly agreeable to the composition for CBSD. Once the component is successfully identified for reuse in one or more software application based on component architecture, it may show signs of disagreement for the different application areas. To moderate these disagreements, an adaptation method is used which is known as “component wrapping”. The wrapping methods are depending on nature of software components available for reuse. As the number of software components eligible for reuse continues to increase, the problem of retrieving them from software components repositories is becoming more and more challenging for the software reuse community. This paper establishes and analyzes effective component retrieval process from component repository for development of component-based software.

Keywords: component-based software Development (CBSD), Component Wrapping, Component repository, Architectural Design, Reuse.

I. Introduction

As the number of software components eligible for reuse continues to increase, the problem of retrieving them from software components repositories is becoming more and more challenging for the software reuse community. This area had been subject to research in the past and continues to be in present also. A component repository with a large collection of components and very little documentation is always very challenging while selecting appropriate software components for reuse in multiple applications. Apart from software components lacking in the documentation, there are other challenging areas for component retrieval processes from component repository like software evolution, ambiguity among the component used for actual requirement software, components lacking in certification and diversity of software used for component development

1.1 Component Retrieval

The efficient retrieval of a component from the component repository is of high priority due to the growing and changing needs of software reuse for the development of component-based software. This will not only improve the ease of software reuse but also improve the overall quality of the CBS in terms of productivity, reliability, development cost and time.

There are two major areas on which retrieval of software component focuses on:

- a) Retrieval method used for selecting the appropriate component.
- b) Classification of Software component

a) Retrieval method used for the software component mainly depends on the way component is organized in the component repository. Basically, component retrieval falls into two complementary categories which include high-level classification techniques which highlight retrieval by component category and second low-level cross-reference tool which facilitates various kinds of browsing at the tool level. We are primarily concerned with high-level classification techniques but low-level tools are also needed to establish an important relationship between the components at the code level.

High-level classification of software components is possible through the extraction of the classification information from the component itself or by implementing the classification outline using information about the component that lies outside.

1.2 Identification of Reusable Software Components

The concept of software reuse is continuously refining due to the increasing complexity level in the functional and non-functional requirements of the software. Earlier approaches to software reuse were completely unorganized. Today, complex, high quality, and integrated computer-based systems must be built in a short span of time. This moderates towards a more

organized approach for reuse of software.

1.3 Characteristics for reusable component

Reusable software components reduce development cost, time and typically have a very higher quality value for the proposed software. A component needs to have certain qualities that contribute to its reusability. These characteristics required for reuse of software components are as summarized in the table mentioned below:

Table 1.1: Characteristics for Reuse of software component

S.NO	Characteristics
1.	A component is functionally required for future implementation.
2.	Component's function is shared within the specified domain.
3.	Portable across hardware and operating system between different implementations.
4.	Design optimized enough for the next implementation.
5.	A component is reusable in multiple implementations with minor changes only.
6.	Components which are not usable be decomposed to yield reusable components
7.	The component must be certified and testable

2 Classification of Software Component for reuse

The component-based software development approach is very helpful in developing highly reliable, complex and economical software. The basic element for developing such application is preexisting reusable software components.

These reusable software components are placed in a component repository for further reuse broadly classified into two types:

2.1 Reuse without a change in preexisting component

During CBSD most of the software components are considered for reuse without any further modification or change. Various informal and formal criteria for reuse of software components are explored during the literature survey. They are like hands-on experience on a new component, user experiences with components used in past and feedback of the customer. Amongst them, the success rate is very high for the hand-on experience method. The hands-on experience method of component reuse leads to observant remarks of each reusable component in the utmost reliable environment. Researchers and practitioners from CBSE have made effort to apply some of the object-oriented metrics which is also applicable in accessing the

reusability of CBS.

A software component can be highly reusable if the component developer can improve its portability, interoperability, and customizability. Systematic documentation of the component can improve its understandability for the component user which is normally purchased from a third party and finally its overall reusability. During the study of related work of various researchers, many significant points are emphasized which can offer appropriate guidelines to the component user at the time of selecting reusable components from components repository

Fig 1.1: Reuse Model based on a preexisting component without change.

2.2 Reuse with customization in preexisting component

During the selection process of the component from the repository, if the proposed component is not completely fulfilling the requirement, then we move further for modification of existing component which is not an easy choice. This is because of the black-box nature of the component where the source code is unavailable. Lack of proper documentation, use of components in the different operating environments, different business logic and hardware environment are few more challenges for modification of software components

Figure 1.2: Reuse Model using pre-existing component after the change

When the reuse model is applied with customization, in that case, it is required to recognize those parts of the components modifications is a must. Even after modification, the components need to be systematically tested before plugging it into a new application. Therefore, in such a scenario we prefer to have in house developed components. Selection of the such in house component for reusability is decided on the basis of which component is more easily adapted and has less dependability with other components

3. Guidelines for improving the reusability of customized software components

A software component repository arranges, supplies, and manages reusable components. The majority of the software component from the repository are black box in nature where implementation details are entirely hidden from the component user. Some of the components often supporting multiple versions of the components.

Few guidelines to assist component integrator for creation of new reusable components:

- a) A component should have a modest and smaller code structure,
- b) The language used for development should be platform-independent
- c) Documentation for a reusable component should be easy to understand.

Figure 1.3 Component selection for Improving Reusability with Customization

While considering white box component for reuse with customization then the above three rules found more suitable for developing component-based system. In this method, the candidate component is rank high. Good documentation of software components always simplifies the problem faced by the component integrator which is complex and challenging. Simple program structure and small size code easily reduce the complexity and failure rate. The reuse of components is much easier if the code structure is well understood. It helps in better understandability and dependability analysis among the component. Overall understanding of simple code structure helps in improving reliability and reducing the maintainability of complex software. It also improves the fast retrieval method of the desired component from the component repository.

4 Proposed Framework for Component-Based Software Development with Effective Reuse

In order to build complex and large software systems, software integrators always prefer to select components of a smaller size. Component of smaller size is easy to retrieve from the component repository and also easy to manage. The selection of smaller component sizes helps in reducing risk and improving reusability during the development of a software system. These smaller software components are integrated to make the entire software system with less effort, time and cost

Figure 1.4: Framework for component selection and evaluation

Different approaches have been discussed by researchers and practitioners for the selection

and evaluation of software component. Most of them are lacking in providing a framework where component integrators can select and evaluate a software component with a high degree of ease and develop software of very high quality. Based on proposed frame the set of activities and action proposed is summarised in the table given bellow

Table 2: Activities and action taken for the proposed framework

Step	Activity	Condition	Action
1	Start		Select component
2	Selection of domain specific Component		Compare functionality
3	Comparing functionality of selected component with required Component	Matches?	If Yes → Step 4, If No → Go back to Step 2
4	Comparing actual component cost with estimated cost of the component	Actual ≤ Estimated?	If Yes → Purchase, If No → Step 5
5	Cost Negotiation with the multiple vendor	Negotiation successful?	If Yes → Purchase, If No → Step 6
6	Check for alternative components available	Alternative available?	If Yes → Return to Step 3, If No → Step 7
7	Check for customized component	Customized available?	f Yes → Adopt customized component, If No → Step 8
8	Final decision		Develop in-house OR purchase from other vendors
9	End		

Using the proposed framework, even a less experienced component integrator can select the component which is available in the specified domain with the desired standard. The functionality of the components proposed for reuse is compared with the expected functionality of the component. Once we find desired functionality with the proposed component then its actual cost is compared with the estimated cost of the component. Once we find that the cost of buying the component is less than or equal to the estimated cost then we prefer to buy this component from the component vendors. Otherwise, if the cost of the component is higher than its estimated cost then we prefer to go for cost negotiation. After a successful negotiation component is purchased. If negotiation is not successful then we even think of alternative components available for reuse. If we do not find an alternative component then we look for customized software component which can be helpful in reducing cost and development time. If we find trouble in identifying customized

component then organization prefer to develop its own component or purchase the component from suitable vendors.

References

- [1] Amit Verma, Monisha Kumari and Iqbal deep Kaur, (2017) “Software Component Retrieval using Keyword- Based Search Technique” *International Journal of Computer Science and Information security* Vol. 15, No 1.
- [2] X. Qu *et al.*, "Research on Component Retrieval and Matching Methods," *2022 International Seminar on Computer Science and Engineering Technology (SCSET)*, Indianapolis, IN, USA, 2022, pp. 358-362, doi: 10.1109/SCSET55041.2022.00087.
- [3] Sampath Korra, S. Viswanadha Raju, and A. Vinaya Babu (2013) “Strategies for Designing and Building Reusable Software Components” *International Journal of Computer Science and Information security* Vol. 4, No 5.
- [4] Arun Sharma, Rajesh Kumar and P S Grover (2006), "Investigation of reusability, complexity and customizability for component-based systems", *ICFAI Journal of IT*, Vol.2 Issue. 1,
- [5] Loveleen Kaur and Dr. Hardeep Singh, (2014), “Software Component Selection techniques-A review”, *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies*, Vol. 5, Issue 3,
- [6] Muhammad Tahir, Fazlullah Khan, Muhammad Babar, Fahim Arif and Shahzad Khan (2016), “Framework for Better Reusability in Component-Based Software Engineering” *Journal of Applied Environmental and Biological Sciences*. ISSN: 2090- 4274.
- [7] Osheen Bhardwaj and Shambhu Kumar Jha (2017), “Quality Assurance Through soft computing technique in CBSE” *International Conference on Smart Technology for Smart Nation*.
- [8] Lei Zhang, Lichaon Chen, Lihu Pan and Yingjun Zhang (2012), “A Novel Approach of Component Retrieval in Large-Scale Component Repositories”, *IEEE*
- [9] Shambhu Kumar Jha and R. K. Mishra, “A Review on Reusability of ComponentBased Software Development” *Reliability: Theory and Applications (RTA)* ISSN: 1932-2321, Volume-14, Issue-4, Page No: 32-36, December 2019.
- [10] Sakshi Patel and Jagdeep Kaur (2016), “A Study of Component-Based SoftwareSystem Metrics” in *International Conference on Computing, Communication and Automation (ICCCA)*